

UV Lithographic Patterning on Spin-coated DNA Thin-films

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ABSTRACT

Photopatterning with 266 nm UV light was accomplished on spin-coated DNA thin films using two different techniques. Lithographic masks were used to create 10-100 micron-sized arrays of enhanced hydrophilicity. Two such masks were used: (1) Polka Dot Filter having opaque squares and a transparent grid and (2) A metal wire-mesh having transparent squares and opaque grid. UV light selectively photodissociates the DNA film where it is exposed into smaller more hydrophilic fragments. UV-exposed films are then coated with a solution of a protein. The protein appears to selectively coat over areas exposed to UV light. We have also used interferometric lithography with UV light to accomplish patterning on the scale of 1 micron on DNA thin films. This technique has the potential to generate micro/nano arrays and vary the array-size. This paper describes the fabrication of these microarrays and a plausible application for fabricating antibody arrays for protein sensing applications.

Keywords: UV lithography, DNA, microarrays, protein sensing

1. INTRODUCTION

The material demand for innovative optical devices with high performance is rapidly increasing. Design, synthesis and optimization of selective materials are necessary to meet the growing demands for state of the art optical devices such as ultra-fast communication systems and chemical/biological molecular recognition sensors. Aggressive research is being conducted to meet those challenges. In particular, Air Force researchers are investigating salmon DNA as the primary ingredient in the design of optical waveguide devices. DNA as a functional biomaterial shows great promise in the development of chemical/biological sensing device applications¹⁻⁵.

This research effort is an extension of the already existing work that is being conducted using DNA in RXPS. Marine-derived DNA is now being studied and characterized both as a waveguide core and as a cladding layer in electro-optic devices based on nonlinear optic polymers. As a potential cladding, this material exhibits the necessary electrical and optical properties. Current studies have shown that the DNA media have high optical transparency over a broad spectral range, from visible to near IR. The mechanical structure of the DNA appears to be thermally stable without visible degradation up to 200°C. It is highly water soluble and biodegradable. Because DNA is derived from waste material (salmon fishing industry), it is therefore abundant and inexpensive. Recent studies have shown that DNA may prove to be a more suitable biomaterial than conventional polymers currently being used for optical devices.

The work described here deals with DNA thin-film substrates for fabricating micro-array and nano-arrays with the potential for fabricating protein sensors. Patterning of these arrays is accomplished by UV lithography using masks as well as interferometric lithography. Recently, several polymers have been investigated for their application as substrates for binding biomolecules for sensing applications. Poly-L-lysine is an amino-acid polymer. Due to its hydrophilicity it is commonly used as a coating agent to promote cell adhesion in culture as well as for immobilization of oligonucleotides in DNA microarrays⁶. Subsequent UV-light exposure is used to cross-link oligonucleotides to the PLL surface. As an alternative technique, it is seen that if some polymers are treated with UV light, their hydrophilicity increases⁷⁻¹⁰. Some

examples include enhanced hydrophilicity in polymethylsilsesquixane nanoporous films⁹ as well as thin films of PMMA⁵ which results in enhanced wettability due to formation of carboxylic acid groups. In other polymers, polar groups such as hydroxyl, carbonyl and carboxylic acids⁹⁻¹² are reported. Most of this photopatterning has been accomplished using 185 and 254 nm emission from mercury discharge lamps although patterning for increased hydrophilicity has also been accomplished using plasma in oxygen atmosphere¹³.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

The purified DNA received from Japan is initially water soluble. It is precipitated with a cationic surfactant, hexadecyltrimethylammonium chloride (CTMA) to render it water insoluble. The resulting DNA-CTMA complex is not only water insoluble but more mechanically stable due to the long alkyl chain of the CTMA. DNA-CTMA is soluble in most alcohol based solvents and aqueous solutions. A set of experiments was developed to determine if DNA is a suitable and efficient material for UV lithography patterning. An understanding of the homogeneous double helical structure of the DNA will provide insight on how to proceed with the design of chemical/biological sensing devices.

Eight different solutions were prepared for this study of the DNA-CTMA dissolved in a butanol based system. These concentrations are (1) 10 wt %; 200K mW; 1500rpm, (2) 10 wt %; 200K mW; 1000rpm, (3) 5%; 400K mW; 1500rpm, (4) 10 wt %; 400K mW; 1500rpm, (5) 5 wt %; 500K mW; 1500rpm, (6) 5 wt %; 1million mW; 1500rpm, (7) 5 wt %; 1 million mW; 1000rpm and (8) 12 wt %; 200K mW; 1000rpm, where mW is the molecular weight and rpm is the spin-coating speed.

Spin-coated DNA thin-films were exposed to 266 nm UV light through two lithographic masks: (1) Polka Dot Filter having opaque squares and a transparent grid and (2) A metal wire-mesh having transparent squares and opaque grid. In each case, the size of squares was 100 micron x 100 micron. DNA films are typically exposed for 20-30 minutes with the UV beam having a power of 10 mW and diameter of 1 mm. Figure 1 shows a schematic of lithographic masks used in this work.

Figure 1. Lithographic masks used for photopatterning DNA substrates with UV light

UV light selectively destroys the DNA film where it is exposed. UV-exposed films are then coated with a saturated solution of a protein, Streptavidin tagged to a hydrophilic dye, Oregon Green in water. The protein appears to selectively coat over areas exposed to UV light, i.e. areas with fragmented-DNA film. The coated areas are then made visible by exposing to 473 nm diode laser. The photopatterning technique with masks is useful for fabricating arrays in 10-100 micron-size range. For smaller feature-size, the masks can result in edge effects due to diffraction and so are not very suitable. A technique which overcomes this limitation and can be used to fabricate nano-scale arrays involves

interferometric lithography. While masks can be used with UV light from mercury lamps, one needs coherent UV light from a laser for interferometric lithography. The set-up for the latter technique is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: experimental setup for interferometric technique: The UV laser beam is split into two diverging beams which are then folded by a set of two mirrors and interfere on the surface of the film. Each of the UV beams makes an angle of 3.5 degrees with the normal to the surface, resulting in a grating period of around 2 microns. The monitoring low power (5 mW), 632 nm He-Ne laser beam is incident normally to the DNA-film. The growth is seen on any of the first order diffraction of the He-Ne laser.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Interference of coherent UV laser beams on DNA thin film results in a grating of alternating hydrophilicity. Sequential fabrication of two perpendicular gratings results in arrays. Fabrication of arrays can also be accomplished with simultaneous interference of three or more coherent UV beams. As the hydrophilicity-grating is being fabricated, it is monitored in real-time by diffraction of a weak (5 mW) He-Ne laser as shown in figure above. In this work, interferometric lithography was accomplished with a 10 mW UV laser at a wavelength of 266 nm. Laser power on the DNA substrate is about 2 mW per laser beam. The primary laser beam is split into two coherent diverging beams by a phase mask. The two diverging beams are then folded by a set of two mirrors and interfere on the surface of the film. Each of the UV beams makes an angle of 3.5 degrees with the normal to the surface, resulting in a grating period of around 2 microns. Diffracted He-Ne light becomes visible in less than five minutes. With 2 mW per beam, it takes about 30 minutes for the diffraction efficiency to reach its maximum although with increased laser power this time is proportionately shortened. A maximum absolute efficiency of about 1% has been observed for each of the first-order diffracted beams. The grating parameter or the spacing between grating lines limits the feature-size that can be fabricated by this technique. The grating parameter (Λ) is given in equation 1.

$$\Lambda = \frac{\lambda_{UV}}{2 \cdot \sin(\theta)} \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

Thus for an angle between the UV beams of 45° (Fig. 2) and λ_{UV} of 266 nm, $\Lambda = 200$ nm. Clearly, this technique has the potential to fabricate nano-scale arrays. Additionally, the feature-size can be changed simply by changing the angle between interfering UV beams. This can be compared to lithography with masks where each mask is good only for one unique photopattern. Micrographs of these arrays are shown in Fig. 3. Micrograph 3a is an array formed by the lithographic mask of Fig. 2a. Square regions exposed to UV light become hydrophilic while the unexposed grid is hydrophobic. Thus, when this array is coated with a protein, which is tagged with a hydrophilic dye, the dye sticks only to UV-exposed hydrophilic areas. Likewise, the micrograph 3b is made with the lithographic mask 2b. This mask has a

transparent grid and an opaque array of squares. Once again, hydrophilic dye attached to Streptavidin protein binds only to the UV-exposed hydrophilic areas on DNA thin film, i.e. on the grid. To make these protein microarrays, the substrate is coated with one drop of a solution of dye-tagged protein in water for 10-15 minutes and then washed with water. The hydrophilic patterns are made visible by the hydrophilic fluorescing dye, Oregon Green. The fluorescence is excited with a 473 nm laser. Hydrophilic areas with immobilized protein appear green when viewed through a suitable filter to remove laser light.

This technique of coating antibodies has the potential for the fabrication of micro- and nano-array protein sensors. Clearly, more work needs to be done to improve the quality of patterning and understand the binding of protein to UV-exposed DNA

Figure 3: Optical micrograph of DNA thin film exposed to UV light with a mesh (figure 3a) and with a polka dot neutral density filter (figure 3b) and coated with Streptavidin attached to Oregon Green. The fluorescence of the dye is excited using a 473 nm light. The exciting light is removed with a 473 nm filter. Figure 3c is a micrograph of a grating fabricated by interferometric lithography on DNA thin film followed by coating with Streptavidin attached to Oregon Green

4. CONCLUSION

It was shown that Marine derived DNA offers an obvious avenue as a substrate for the binding of proteins/antibodies and for development of chemical/biological micro/nanoarray sensors. Due to bio-compatibility of DNA, with further characterization of this recently explored biomaterial, marine-derived DNA may prove to be a more suitable material than conventional polymeric materials currently used for such optical devices/sensors.

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6. REFERENCES

- [1] Wang L., Yoshida J., Ogata N., Sasaki S., and Kajiyama T., "Self-Assembled Supramolecular Films Derived from Marine Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA)-Cationic Surfactant Complexes: Large-Scale Preparation and Optical and Thermal Properties", *Chem. Mater.* 13(4), 1273-1281 (2001).
- [2] Yaney P. P., Heckman E. M., Diggs D. E., Hopkins F. K., and Grote J. G., "Development of chemical sensors using polymer optical waveguides fabricated with DNA", *Proc. SPIE*, 5724, 224-233 (2005).
- [3] Heckman E. M., Grote J. G., Yaney P. P., and Hopkins F. K., "DNA-based nonlinear photonic materials", *Proc. SPIE*, 5516, 47-51 (2004).
- [4] Wang L., Ishihara K., Izumi H., Wada M., Zhang G., Ishikawa T., Watanabe A., Horinouchi S., and Ogata N., "Strongly luminescent rare-earth ion-doped DNA-CTMA complex film and fiber materials", *Proc. SPIE*, 4905, 143-153 (2002).
- [5] Zhang G., Takahashi H., Wang L., Yoshida J., Kobayahi S., Horinouchi S., and Ogata N., "Nonlinear Optical Materials Derived from Biopolymer (DNA)-surfactant-Azo dye complex", *Proc. SPIE* 4905, 375-380 (2002).
- [6] Vivian, G. C.; Morley, M.; Aguilar, F.; Massimi, A.; Kucherlapati, R.; Childs, G. "Making and reading microarrays", *Nature Genetics supplement*, 21, 15-19 (1999).
- [7] Kowal, J.; Czajkowska, B.; Bulwan, E.; Blazewicz, M.; Pamula, E., "Modification of polysulfone by means of UV irradiation and H₂O₂ plasma treatment", *European Cells and Materials*, 7, 59 (2004).
- [8] Zouali, M.; Stollar, B. D.; "A rapid ELISA for measurement of antibodies to nucleic acid antigens using UV-treated polystyrene microplates", *J. Immunol. Methods* 90, 105-110 (2004).
- [9] Kim, H.-C.; Wallragff G.; Kreller, C. R.; Angelos, S.; Lee, V. Y.; Volksen, W.; Miller, R. D., "Photopatterned nanoporous media", *Nano Lett.* 4, 1169-1174 (2004).
- [10] McCarley, R. L.; Vaidya, B.; Wei, S.; Smith, A. F.; Patel, A. B.; Feng, J.; Murphy, M. C.; Soper, S. A., "Resist-free patterning of surface architectures in polymer-based microanalytical devices", *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 127(3), 842-843 (2005).
- [11] Hozumi, A.; Masuda T.; Hayashi K.; Sugimura H.; Takai O.; Kameyama T., "Spatially Defined Surface Modification of Poly(methyl methacrylate) Using 172 nm Vacuum Ultraviolet Light", *Langmuir*, 18, 9022-9027 (2002).
- [12] Weikart, C. M.; Yasuda, H. K., "Modification, degradation, and stability of polymeric surfaces treated with reactive plasmas", *J. Polym. Sci., A: Polym. Chem.* 38, 3028-3042 (2000).
- [13] Langowski, B. A.; Uhrich, K. E., "Microscale Plasma-Initiated Patterning (μ PIP)", *Langmuir*, 21, 10509-10514 (2005).